

A PERCEPTUAL ANALYSIS OF OWERRI BOSS RADIO DRUG SENSITISATION CAMPAIGN AGAINST HARD DRUG USE AND ITS EFFECT ON OWERRI YOUTHS

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ABSTRACT

The researchers in this study sought to find out the behavioural effect of radio drug sensitisation campaigns on Owerri youth's perception and behaviour. This study was anchored on the health belief theory. This study employed a survey research design and used the questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. The population of 589,564 was used to represent Owerri Metropolis residents. Wimmer and Dominick online sample size calculator was used to arrive at a sample size of 384. The purposive and multi-stage sampling techniques were employed in the study. Finding gotten from the study revealed that Owerri residents are exposed to Boss FM radio campaign against hard drug at a high level. Finding as well showed that at an average mean score of 3.2 that radio campaign against hard drug has had a positive effect on Owerri youth's behaviour; they no longer use or abuse drugs, now sensitize others against hard drug use or abuse, as well as now choose sane friends who are not drug users. Based on the finding, it was concluded that hard drugs should be universally avoided by young people and all other drug users in Nigeria, since they have a serious negative effect on everyone who uses them, not just the victim or addict. The researchers recommend that drug enforcement authorities need to be proactive in ensuring the success of anti-drug addiction campaigns and should have a treatment plan in place for willing drug addicts who want to stop using drugs.

Key words: Drug sensitisation campaign, effects, perceptive, radio, youths

Introduction

Over time, people get dependent on any substance, even something as simple as coffee. This study's case involves heavy drug usage, abuse, and addiction. In order to improve their mood, feelings, and sensitivity, some humans have peculiar reasons for needing love, devotion, prayers, and hard drugs (Sussman et al., 2011; Wardle & de Wit, 2012; McVeigh, et al., 2012). As a result, drug use has turned into a necessity for humans. According to Wardle and de Wit (2012), amphetamine will increase response to pleasurable stimuli, especially those that include a social component, and these effects will be regardless of the drug's direct effects on mood. A new and expanding user base has been created by the widely available medications that have the potential to enhance human characteristics, looks, and talents (McVeigh, et al, 2012).

Alcohol, amphetamines, barbiturates, benzodiazepines, cannabis, cocaine, hallucinogens, methaqualone, and opioids are commonly associated with the term "drug," according to World Drug Report (2014), although the exact root of substance abuse is unknown, there are two leading theories: either a hereditary predisposition or a habit picked up from others that, if it becomes an addiction, presents as a

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chronic, crippling illness. Hard drug in form of illicit and recurrent drug has been shown to have negative health effects on people. Humans frequently turn to using hard drugs without a prescription from a doctor, and in some circumstances they grow accustomed to these self-prescribed medications in order to feel normal (Ritchie, 2019). It is extremely bad to use drugs in quantities or ways that are detrimental to the user since it can lead to fatal substance use disorders. In most developed countries, drug abuse has recently been shown to be the main factor contributing to injury fatalities (Yunusa, 2022).

About 5% of individuals (230 million) use illicit substances, according to Chakravarthy, et al. (2013), who also emphasise the impact that frequent and illicit drug use does to health. Of these, 27 million use high-risk drugs on a regular basis, which can have negative health effects, psychological issues, or social issues. This puts them at risk of these dangers. The number of deaths caused by substance use disorders increased from 165,000 in 1990 to 307,400 in 2015. According to McClellan (2017) and Ritchie (2019), the biggest numbers of these deaths are caused by alcohol use disorders (137,500), opioid use disorders (122,100), amphetamine use disorders (12,200), and cocaine use disorders (11,100).

According to the Centres for Disease Control (CDC), (2021), and Hedegaard, et al, (2020), there were 70,630 drug overdose deaths worldwide as of 2019, an increase of 4.8% from 67,367 in 2018. Opioids, which accounted for 70.6% of all drug overdose deaths in 2019, have been contributing to a rising number of drug overdose deaths since 2009. In recent years, drug overdose deaths have also been associated with an increased use of cocaine and psychostimulants with abuse potential (Mattson, et al, 2021; Hedegaard, et al., 2021). The age-adjusted death rate from drug misuse was 21.6 per 100,000 people in 2019.

In terms of hard drug use among Nigerians, statistics on drug misuse revealed that more than 11% of the country's youth population use substances like syrup, tramadol, diazepam, cocaine, and shisha mix, among others (Onyedika-Ugoeze, 2019). According to Onyedika-Ugoeze, 2019), given that young people are engaging in serious drug misuse, the health implications of the aforementioned number are quite depressing and concerning. According to current figures from the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA), 40% of Nigerian teenagers between the ages of 18 and 35 are heavily involved in drug misuse (*Premium Times Agency Report*, 2021).

In the daily lives of many individuals, radio listening took precedence over TV and the usage of more modern digital listening devices. As a result, the radio occupies a special place in the hearts of many individuals; some do so out of habit or to satisfy their sense of nostalgia (Krause, 2020). Most often, people turn to listening to the radio in order to pass the time and avoid loneliness (Order, 2017). Unless handled from a psychological perspective, audiences frequently lack a deeper grasp of consuming motivations and results (Krause & North, 2016).

The mass media social transformation roles and uses their influence to address societal issues (Edubirdie, 2023). Radio programmes and jingles have demonstrated a powerful ability to sway listeners' opinions, values, and behaviour. They can also persuade them to purchase a wide range of goods and services and educate them on important topics, such as the dangers of hard drug use for both youths and other people (Psychology Today, 2022; Iheanacho et al., 2021). Since the number of radio listeners is rising, radio programmes are stated to inspire, dissuade, and empower radio audiences (UNESCO Courier, 2020). Therefore, it is generally accepted that radio can be used to persuade people to take action in support of their personal health and well-being or to "do right" by significant societal concerns. Based on this supposition, since World War II, the federal, state, and local governments, private foundations, and other nongovernmental organisations have funded hundreds of public service announcements that encourage social awareness about a problem rather than just about a commercial "goods" (Indeed Editorial Team, 2023; Hendricks, 2021).

Nearly all radio stations in Owerri have run radio campaigns against drug addiction, but one of them features a radio jingle by Evang Mike Ikoku that educates listeners about drugs. Mike Ikoku may be heard on Boss 98.9 FM and BizziBodi 100.1 FM. This particular jingle on “*Mkpurummiri*” (Crystal Meth.) is thought to be the drug education programme that is broadcasted frequently in these two radio stations. This jingle against “*Mkpurummiri*” aims at helping hard drug users change their habits, so as to experience the desired transformation their life needs. The first Igbo/Pidgin radio stations in Nigeria are these ones owned by Evang. Mike Ikoku. This campaign against hard drugs and their abuse was launched by Mike Ikoku on December 21st, 2021 (Otown Gist, 2023). This campaign jingle is played by each programme host on Boss FM, BizziBodi FM, and other Owerri radio stations. The goal of this radio campaign against hard drug usage is to persuade young people not to use these drugs by pleading with them about the drugs harmful, short and long-term impacts (Quin Gist, 2023).

Statement of the problem

The importance of the radio medium cannot be over emphasized. Radio being the most peculiar broadcast media to the masses has used their sensitization programmes and jingles to set informative, educational and life changing agenda to their heterogeneous listeners. Owerri radio stations use their jingles to sensitize, inform, educate and persuade their listeners towards a particular course of action and information they need to know about. Boss FM campaign against hard drug is well prominent among Owerri residents and youths, however, there might be some perceived hindrances on why Boss radio 98.9 sensitisation may have little effect on drug addicts. Some radio listeners in most occasions see radio jingles as nothing serious but a way of getting good words, rhymes and concept together for the listening pleasure and moral boosting of the radio listeners. Most youths do not even take the fight against hard drug serious, they see most of the jingle content to be overhyped and untrue, although in few cases they perceive same jingle content to be factual. Youths understanding of radio sensitization messages against hard drug use, which are aired in form of programmes or jingles affect the effect it has on them. In line with the above stated problems, the researchers in this study sought to know the effect of Boss 98.9 FM’s sensitization campaigns against hard drug on Owerri youth’s perception on hard drug.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following questions, which are to;

1. What is the level of exposure of residents of Owerri Metropolis to hard drug campaigns on Boss Radio 98.9FM?
2. What are the perceptions of Owerri youths on hard drug?
3. What are the perceptible behavioural effects of Boss Radio 98.9FM hard drug campaign on youths in Owerri Metropolis?

Scope of the Study

This study is limited to Owerri Metropolis residents in Imo state since, it is impossible or almost impossible to study the entire state. The study is as well limited to Owerri residents, especially the youths who listen to Boss 98.9 FM and are exposed to Boss FM radio campaigns against hard drug intake, abuse and addiction. This study is focused on how Boss Radio 98.9FM hard drug campaigns have had an effect on Owerri youths use, abuse, or addiction to hard drugs.

Literature Review

Drug Use and Abuse

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According to World Health Organization (2003), psychoactive drugs are chemical substances that affect the function of the central nervous system, altering perception, mood or consciousness. These drugs are divided into different groups like: stimulants, depressants, antidepressants, anxiolytics, antipsychotics, and hallucinogens. These psychoactive drugs have been proven useful in treating wide range of medical conditions including mental disorders around the world. The most widely used drugs in the world include caffeine, nicotine and alcohol, which are also considered recreational drugs, since they are used for pleasure rather than medicinal purposes. Mahoney and Evans (2008) opined that all drugs can have potential side effects. Abuse of several psychoactive drugs can cause addiction and/or physical dependence. Excessive use of stimulants can promote stimulant psychosis. Many recreational drugs are illicit and international treaties such as the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs exist for the purpose of their prohibition.

According to WHO (2003), substance abuse refers to the harmful or hazardous use of psychoactive substances, including alcohol and illicit drugs. One of the key impacts of illicit drug use on society is the negative health consequences experienced by its members. Drug use also puts a heavy financial burden on individuals, families and society. The evolution of the complex global illicit drug problem is clearly driven by a range of factors. Cannabis remains the most widely used illicit substance in the African Region. (WHO, 2022) The highest prevalence and increase in use is being reported in West and Central Africa with rates between 5.2% and 13.5% (WHO, 2021).

Amphetamine type stimulants (ATS) such as "ecstasy" and methamphetamine now rank as Africa's second most widely abused drug type. Other substances that were used by children and youth surveyed in Sierra Leone, included benzodiazepines such as diazepam, chlorpromazine and different inhalants, while 3.7% were injecting drugs. Injecting drugs carries a high risk of infection with bloodborne viruses such as HIV, hepatitis B and hepatitis C, and the sharing of contaminated needles and syringes is an important mode of transmission for those viruses (WHO, 2022).

Nigerians Commonly Used Hard Drugs

According to Jatau, et al. (2021), and Ochuo (2021), Nigerians use and misuse the following hard drugs the most frequently. Almost every chemical whose consumption can provide a euphoric (high) feeling is abuseable by people. Many people are aware of the abuse of legal substances like alcohol or criminal substances like marijuana (which is outlawed in most states) and cocaine, but less is known about the abuse of inhalants such household cleansers and over-the-counter pharmaceuticals like cold remedies. Public Health Nigeria (2023) and BYJU (2023) outlines the numerous substances and drug classes that people frequently abuse and/or become dependent on include the following:

Alcohol: Despite being legal, alcohol is harmful, especially when used by a pregnant woman because it can harm the unborn child.

Amphetamines: This class of pharmaceuticals includes both legally produced drugs like methamphetamine (often known as "crystal meth") and illegally produced drugs like methylphenidate (such as Ritalin, Concerta, and Focalin), as well as dextro-amphetamine and amphetamine (Adderall). Any of these chemicals taken in excess might cause convulsions and even death.

Anabolic steroids: A class of medications that bodybuilders and other athletes most frequently abuse, these chemicals can cause terrible mental side effects like anger and paranoia as well as serious long-term medical side effects like infertility and organ failure.

Caffeine: Although many people drink coffee, tea, and soda, excessive consumption of caffeine can have habit-forming effects and cause palpitations, sleeplessness, tremors, irritability, and considerable anxiety.

Cannabis: this is tetrahydrocannabinol (THC), most commonly known as marijuana. Cannabis is its scientific name. In the past year, approximately 14 million persons aged 12 or older reported using marijuana, making it the most widely used illicit substance. The fact that the drug is frequently combined (cut) with other substances so that drug dealers can profit more from the sale of the diluted substance or expose the user to more addictive drugs and the risks associated with those added substances is in addition to the harmful effects the drug itself can cause (for example, infertility, difficulties with sexual performance, paranoia, lack of motivation). Baby powder, oregano, embalming fluid, phencyclidine (PCP), opiates, cocaine, and baby powder are among the chemicals that are frequently used to cut marijuana.

Cathinones (bath salts): Chemically unrelated to bath salts that people use to bathe, cathinone are chemically similar to stimulant drugs, like amphetamines, cocaine, and Ecstasy (MDMA). In addition to bath salts, other street names for cathinone include "plant food," "jewelry cleaner," or "phone screen cleaner."

Cocaine: A drug that tends to stimulate the nervous system, people can snort cocaine in powder form, smoke it when in the form of rocks ("crack" cocaine), or inject it when made into a liquid.

Ecstasy: Also called MDMA to denote its chemical composition (methylenedioxyamphetamine), this drug tends to create a sense of euphoria and an expansive love or desire to nurture others. In overdose, it can increase body temperature to the point of causing death.

Hallucinogens: LSD, mescaline, and naturally occurring hallucinogens like certain mushrooms are some examples of hallucinogens. Due to their capacity to change the user's perceptions, these medicines have the potential to be harmful. Hallucinations and false beliefs brought on by hard drugs can lead to risky behaviours, such as jumping out of a window when one believes one has wings and can fly.

Inhalants: Due to their widespread availability, inhalants are one of the most often abused classes of chemicals. They are typically found in home cleaners like ammonia, bleach, and other fuming substances. Depending on the individual, using an inhalant even only once or repeatedly can cause brain damage that could lead to death.

Nicotine: This is one of the most addicting compounds on earth and is the addictive component of cigarettes. In fact, many individuals liken opiate addiction—which is extremely addictive—to nicotine addiction.

Narcotics or opioids: are other names for this class of pharmaceuticals, which also includes heroin, codeine, hydrocodone, morphine, methadone, Vicodin, OxyContin, Percocet, and Percodan. The nervous system's functionality is drastically reduced by this class of drugs. Opioid abusers frequently have to use higher and higher doses to achieve the same level of intoxication, eventually reaching a point where the dose required to get high is the same as the dose that would cause respiratory arrest in that person in the event of an overdose.

Phencyclidine: this substance has the potential to make the user extremely suspicious, aggressive, and physically extremely strong. Due of this, they may pose a serious threat to others.

Sedatives, hypnotics, and anti-anxiety medications: these are narcotics that calm or depress the nervous system. These chemicals are the second most popular class of illicit narcotics. Therefore, they can result in death by preventing breathing (respiratory arrest) in someone who either overdoses on them or who mixes one or more of them with another substance that depresses the neurological system, such as alcohol, another sedative, or an opiate.

Why People Engage in Hard Drug Usage and Abuse

Most people choose to use drugs on their own volition. However, when kids become entangled in the addiction cycle, their neurological connections change, making it harder for them to maintain control over their behaviour and withstand strong impulsive urges. The more drugs someone uses, the more their brain is trained to look forward to the same drug-induced pleasurable experiences (National Institute on Drug Abuse [NIDA], 2023). That is why stopping is so challenging. One's tolerance may eventually increase to the point where addictive behaviour no longer brings pleasure and consuming drugs just becomes a means of avoiding withdrawal. For them to feel normal at all, they require medicines (Fletcher, 2016).

When it comes to hard drug addiction, studies (Tyler, 2016; Varin, 2023; Mayo Clinic, 2023) have stated that not everyone who tries drugs becomes an addiction. Overall social, biological, and environmental factors do raise the likelihood of developing a drug addiction.

Biology: About half of an individual's susceptibility to addiction is determined by genes in conjunction with environmental circumstances. The likelihood of developing an addiction can also be increased by a person's gender, race (especially if they are African American), or mental disease.

Environment: A person's probability of acquiring an addiction is significantly influenced by their family, friends, and socioeconomic situation. Addiction to drugs or alcohol can be significantly influenced by peer pressure, parental advice, stress, and physical and sexual abuse.

Development: Although a person can become an addict at any age, the earlier substance use begins, the more likely it will escalate to serious addiction.

Negative Effects of Hard Drug Use and Addiction

Unfortunately, substance addiction is more responsible for deaths, illnesses, and impairments than any other preventable medical issue (Tyler, 2016). In spite of the fact that various drugs might have detrimental effects that differ from one another, NIDA (2023) gave the following as some typical symptoms that substance addiction can lead to:

1. Damaged immune system, which increases susceptibility to infection
2. Cardiovascular conditions, including heart attacks and collapsed veins
3. Nausea, vomiting, and abdominal pain
4. Liver overexertion or liver failure
5. Seizures and strokes

Widespread brain damage that can interfere with memory, attention, and decision making, as well as permanent brain damage. Some of the worst effects of substance abuse aren't even health related. Drug abuse can have a number of damaging consequences on an addict's social and emotional well-being, including:

1. Loss of employment
2. Relationship loss

3. Incarceration
4. Financial trouble
5. Homelessness
6. Risky sexual behavior

Many problems can be reversed or minimized by getting sober, but there may be some health and emotional issues that simply won't heal with time. The best way to prevent permanent damage is to seek professional drug addiction treatment ASAP to overcome the addiction.

Boss FM Radio Campaign against Drug Abuse

Evang. Micheal Ikoku is a politician with a call to service, a public speaker, and a serial entrepreneur. He is the All seasons CEO and the CEO of NV Broadcasting Company Limited (LinkedIn, 2023). Evang Micheal Ikoku recently received the title of ambassador from the Imo state command of the Nigerian Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA), for his assistance in the fight against drug usage. The NDLEA Imo State command is currently running a campaign against drugs, and Evang. Micheal Ikoku is deliberately broadcasting the campaign. Every day, Michael Amadi can be heard on Boss 98.9 FM and BizziBodi 100.1 FM (Facebook, 2023).

Evang. Micheal Ikoku officially launched the anti-drug abuse campaign on December 21st, 2021. This anti-hard drug campaign is a one (1) minute, one (1) second jingle that informs listeners of the detrimental effects of hard drugs, including both their immediate and long-term effects. This campaign is being broadcast on Facebook and YouTube in addition to BizziBodi FM and Boss FM (Otown Gist, 2023). Evang. Michael Ikoku is involved in this campaign against hard drugs; his entire staff of on-air anchors still concludes the majority of their shows with a warning against hard drug (Quin Gist, 2023).

Review of Empirical studies

Okoye et al.,(2022) research on effectiveness of mass media in the fight against drug abuse among undergraduates found that the level of awareness among respondents towards mass media campaigns against drug abuse is moderate. Further findings showed that respondents agreed that mass media efforts have not been effective in reducing the threat of drug abuse among undergraduates in Imo State's tertiary institutions.

Similarly, a study by Achieng and Kenyagah (2014) comparing print media reports on drug and substance abuse discovered that drug abuse has not been given prominence by the print media and this is because most of the articles published were short items and they appeared on the inside page of the newspapers. This means that only a few people read such items. Therefore, the researcher concluded that print media has not given drug abuse prominence.

Also, Abubakar et al. in (2019), did a scoping review on the burden of drug abuse in Nigeria. Their finding revealed that a prevalence of 20-40% and 20.9% of drug abuse was reported among students and youths, respectively. Commonly abused drugs include cannabis, cocaine, amphetamine, heroin, diazepam, codeine, cough syrup and tramadol. Sources where abusers obtained drugs were pharmacies/patent medicine shops, open drug markets, drug hawkers, fellow drug abusers, friends, and drug pushers. Drug abuse was common among undergraduates and secondary school students, youths, commercial bus drivers, farmers, and sex workers. Reason for use included to increase physical performance, stress and to derive pleasure.

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On the other hand, a 2019 research by Umukoro et al., (2019) on substance abuse found that about 13.97% of the students had taken alcohol, 10.79% had taken tramadol, and 3.81% had taken rohypnol. School and mass media were the main sources of information on drug abuse, while peer pressure was the most predisposing influence towards substance use. Depression and its use as a confidence booster were main reasons given for the substance use. Adolescent substance use and abuse remains an ongoing challenge with a prevalence rate of 19.4% in this study.

Unya, and Onya (2022) study finding show that drug abuse and drug trafficking are on the increase among the Nigerian youths.

Related study by Ochuo (2021) discovered that 18 different drugs were empirically identified as being abused by secondary school students in 9 different states of Nigeria. The observed trend is that alcohol, cannabis, tobacco and cigarettes are the most abused drugs, while drugs that were least abused were cocaine, caffeine, glue, heroine, energy drinks, miraa, rohypnol and tramadol.

James, and Georgopoulos (2023) research on the risk assessment of substance use disorders revealed two primary groupings of SUDs based on their immunogenetic profiles: one group comprised cannabis and cocaine, whereas the other group comprised alcohol, amphetamines, opioids, and “other” dependence. Since each individual possesses 12 HLA alleles, the population HLA-SUD scores were subsequently used to estimate individual risk for each SUD.

Theoretical Framework

This study was built on The Health Belief Theory. The Health Belief Theory was developed in 1950s by social psychologists Irwin M. Rosenstock, Godfrey M. Hochbaum, S. Stephen Kegeles, and Howard Leventhal at the U.S. Public Health Service. The HBM is a disease prevention model with a primary focus on how belief and behavior go hand in hand (Shah.,et al., 2020).

There are six main components of the Health Belief Model. Four of these constructs were main tenets of the theory when it was first developed. Two were added in response to research on the model related to addiction (Boskey, 2023). These components include: perceived severity, perceived susceptibility, perceived benefit and perceived barrier (Shah, et al., 2020; Abraham, & Sheeran, 2015). Perceived barriers to healthy behaviors have been shown to be the single most powerful predictor of whether people are willing to engage in healthy behaviors.

This theory is used to improve health behaviour among people. This theory is very much related to this research topic. The health belief of drug abusers and addict is so strong that they cling to it even if it means that they will die doing it. The stigma of drug addiction is too strong and the human system used to drug gets too attached to it that without such drug the individual cannot feel okay. The drug gets into every part of their organs making it look like it is now a part of their every desire, hunger and thirst.

Methodology

The researcher in this study employed the survey research design and made use of questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. This method is appropriate because it will enable the researchers to sample the opinions of the respondents (Okoro et al., 2019). The population used for this study was the population of the three local governments that make up Owerri Metropolis: Municipal: 127,213, Owerri North: 175,395, Owerri West: 99,265, giving us a total of 401,873. 401,873 was extrapolated using the online population growth calculator at a yearly increase of 2.28% for 17 years, which gave a calculated value of 589,564, which became the population for this study. The population is too large to study. Thus, to ascertain the sample size of the population, the Wimmer & Dominick online sample size calculator was used to arrive

at a population size of 384. The purposive and multi-stage sampling technique was employed for the study. The data was presented in simple percentage tables with its tabular descriptive interpretations.

Data Presentation and Analysis

A 384-copy questionnaire was printed and distributed to residents of Owerri Metropolis by the researcher responsible for gathering the data for this study. Only 382 of the questionnaire's original copies were recovered from the responders. For the purposes of this study, 382 of these copies were examined and presented. With a 99.4% return rate, which is still quite good and trustworthy for the study, we achieved a high success return rate.

Research Question One: What is the level of exposure of residents of Owerri Metropolis to hard drug campaigns on Boss Radio 98.9FM?

Table 1: Level of Exposure to radio campaign on Boss 98.9 FM	Options	Frequency	Percentage
Exposure to Boss FM hard drug campaigns	Yes	382	100
	No	0	0
Total		382	100
Exposure level to Boss FM hard drug campaigns	Very high	114	29.8
	High	146	38.2
	Moderate	85	22.2
	Low	30	7.8
	Very low	7	1.8
Total		382	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Finding from the above table revealed that all the respondents are exposed to Boss 98.9 FM radio campaign against hard drug among youths. As for their level of exposure, at 38.2%, it was shown to be at a high level.

Research Question Two: What are the perceptions of Owerri youths on hard drug?

Table 2: Perceptions of Owerri youths on hard drug	SA	A	D	SD	Mean Score	Decision
Drug abuse can result to several criminal acts by the abuser in the society.	125	179	33	45	3.0052	Accepted
Many Nigerian youths have lost their lives due to addictiveness to certain illicit drugs.	201	167	13	1	3.4869	Accepted
Drug addiction always result to the damage of vital organs in the body of the abuser.	207	173	1	1	3.5340	Accepted
Average Mean				3.0		Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2023

At an average mean score of 3.0, we see that Owerri residents perceive hard drug to result to several criminal acts, loss of lives due to addiction and its hallucinating effects, and results to damage of vital human body organs of the drug victim or addict.

Research Question Three: What are the perceptive behavioural effects of Boss Radio 98.9FM hard drug campaign on youths in Owerri Metropolis?

Table 3: Perceptive behavioural effect of youth after being exposed to Boss radio campaigns against hard drug	SA	A	D	SD	Mean Score	Decision
I no longer use or abuse hard drugs as a result of the enlightenment gotten from the campaign	166	180	29	7	3.3219	Accepted
I now enlighten family, friends and loved ones to desist and resist themselves from any form of drug intake, abuse and addiction	138	192	35	17	3.1806	Accepted
These drug addiction campaigns have helped me in choosing friends who are in their right state of mind	177	139	45	21	3.2356	Accepted
Average Mean				3.2		Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2023

At an average mean score of 3.2, Owerri residents behaviourally no longer use or abuse drugs due to radio sensitization campaign against drug, they even now enlighten their family, friends and loved ones to desist and resist themselves from any form of drug intake, abuse and addiction. They were influenced by the campaign to now be very mindful of the sane friends they keep, especially friends who have nothing to do with hard drug.

Discussion of Findings

Owerri residents are highly exposed to Boss 98.9 FM campaigns against hard drug. Similarly, findings by other research shows that youths pay frequent attention to these anti-drug abuse programmes. According to Unya and Onya's findings from 2022, drug abuse and drug trafficking are on the rise among Nigerian youths, necessitating the creation of media campaigns to combat drug misuse and addiction. Similar findings from Okoye et al., (2022) indicate that respondents have a modest level of awareness of mass media campaigns against drug usage. According to a 2017 study by Kim et al., teens, Twitter users, and Instagram users all reported seeing hazardous substance use-related messages on social media.

Findings at an average mean score of 3.0, we see that Owerri residents perceive hard drug to result to several criminal acts, loss of lives due to addiction and its hallucinating effects, and results to damage of vital human body organs of the drug victim or addict. According to Okoye et al. (2022), attempts made by the media to lessen the risk of drug usage among undergraduates in Imo State's higher institutions have not been successful. According to Abubakar et al., (2019), youngsters utilise drugs to relieve stress, improve physical performance, and find pleasure. According to Umukoro, et al., (2019), narcotics are highly popular among depressed people among young people as a confidence builder.

Boss FM radio campaign against hard drug has had a positive effect on Owerri youths behaviour, at an average mean score of 3.2, they no longer use or abuse drugs, now sensitize others against hard drug use or abuse, as well as now choose sane friends who are not drug users. According to Jamriet al., (2022), the message strategies, language strategies, and media channel strategies all have high levels of efficacy. According to studies by Achieng and Kenyagah (2014) and Excellent (2019), drug addiction has not received much attention from the print media. This is because the majority of the pieces produced were brief and appeared on the inside pages of the newspapers. According to Abubakar, et al., (2019), low socioeconomic status and a lack of formal education are the main risk factors for drug misuse. The health belief six (6) components supports' the above findings, in that it explains how drug addicts health belief affects their actions over time and as well either improve or worsen their health behavior.

Conclusion

Some radio stations have run anti-drug programmes in the Owerri Metropolis, however Boss radio and BizziBodi FM are the most well-known and have the most widespread campaigns. These two radio stations have incorporated their anti-drug campaign into their daily shows to the point where even the presenters periodically urge their listeners to refrain from using drugs and to report drug addicts in their neighbourhood so those people might receive treatment. It was determined that the campaign and fight against drug addiction in Owerri Metropolis are proving to be increasingly effective and have persuaded the majority of radio listeners to now sensitize others to avoid drugs. In conclusion, hard drugs should be universally avoided by young people and all other drug users in Nigeria, since they have a serious negative effect on everyone who uses them, not just the victim or addict.

Recommendations

1. Inhabitants of Owerri Metropolis should not only listen to Boss radio campaigns against drug use, abuse, and addiction, but also try to persuade others to do the same in order to spread awareness of this drug campaign among all Owerri inhabitants.
2. Drug enforcement authorities need to be proactive in ensuring the success of anti-drug addiction campaigns and should have a treatment plan in place for willing drug addicts who want to stop using drugs.
3. Boss Radio should be joined in the fight against drug use, abuse, and addiction by all other radio stations in the Owerri Metropolis, this is highly effective in lowering drug use, abuse, and addiction among adolescents living in Owerri.

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